

Ageing Deterioration of High-Density Polyethylene Cable Spacer under Salt Water Dip Wheel Test

P. Kaewchanthuek, R. Rawonghad, B. Marungsri

Abstract—This paper presents the experimental results of high-density polyethylene cable spacers for 22 kV distribution systems under salt water dip wheel test based on IEC 62217. The strength of anti-tracking and anti-erosion of cable spacer surface was studied in this study. During the test, dry band arc and corona discharge were observed on cable spacer surface. After 30,000 cycles of salt water dip wheel test, obviously surface erosion and tracking were observed especially on the ground end. Chemical analysis results by fourier transforms infrared spectroscopy showed chemical changed from oxidation and carbonization reaction on tested cable spacer. Increasing of C=O and C=C bonds confirmed occurrence of these reactions.

Keywords—Cable spacer, HDPE, ageing of cable spacer, salt water dip wheel test.

I. INTRODUCTION

RESENTLY, high-density polyethylene (HDPE) cable spacer has been widely used in power transmission and distribution system. HDPE cable spacers have advantages of low cost, light weight and low electric field stress when comparing with the ceramic type. After long time in service, surface of HDPE cable spacer became inferior and dust was accumulated. Cable spacer would be cleaned by rain difficultly. As a result, leakage current was undesirably increased and electrical insulation characteristics of cable spacer were decreased. There were several reasons for cable spacer deteriorations such as manufacturing processes, material selections, and product designs. Another important factor was the service environment such as tropical climate and high UV intensity [1]-[4].

Basically, the problem of high electric-field concentration on the contact points between the covered conductor and spacer or ties cannot be controlled. This problem has been studied by [5]-[7]. Performances of cable space have been evaluated by many researchers [4], [8]-[10]

Numbers of HDPE cable spacer were use in distribution system of Provincial Electricity Authority of Thailand (PEA) and Metropolitan Electricity Authority of Thailand (MEA). Damaged cable spacers during service were reported by these electric utilities [3]. However, no ageing characteristic of HDPE cable spacer were studied in Thailand. By this reason, this paper reports the experimental study on ageing deterioration of high-density polyethylene cable spacer for 22

kV PEA distribution system in Thailand under salt water dip wheel test.

II. TEST ARRANGEMENTS

A. Specimen

Polymer cable spacers made of high-density polyethylene by injection molding for 22 kV PEA distribution system were used in this study. Configuration and dimension of specimen are illustrated in Fig. 1. As illustrated in Fig. 1, leakage distance between phase A to ground and between phase B to ground is approximately 310mm.

Fig. 1 Configuration and dimensions of specimen

B. Test Arrangement

Four items of cable spacers were installed on the wheel as shown in Fig. 2. Only two phases near ground end were energized. Voltage was energized via stainless rods and stainless sphere as shown in Fig. 3

Fig. 2 Specimen installation

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Fig. 3 Voltage Energized via Stainless Rod and Stainless Sphere

C. Test Method

Test methods for salt water dip wheel test were based on IEC 62217 [11]. Test was conducted continuously for 30,000 cycles. As illustrated in Fig. 2, one test cycle takes time 192 second and includes 4 test positions, energized, de-energized, salt water dip and de-energized, respectively. For each position, test specimen remains stationary for about 40 second and takes 8 second for rotate to the next position. Salt water was re-newed every week and re-newing time must less than 1 hour.

D. Test Conditions

Test was conducted based on test conditions in IEC 62217, as illustrated in Table I. Test voltage was generated from 22 kV, 30 kVA single phase transformer.

TABLE I
 TEST CONDITIONS

Test Voltage	AC 15 kV continuously applied
Voltage stress	48.4 V/mm
NaCl content of de-ionized water	1.4 kg/m [±] 0.06 kg/m ³
Test duration(1 cycle = 192 second)	30,000 cycles

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Visual Observation

During test, many discharge activities were observed. Dry band arc and corona discharge were often observed on the ground end, trunk and energized end. Especially on the ground end was observed severe arcing. Yellow light paths indicate dry band arcing and purple light indicate corona discharges [12] as show in Fig. 4. This phenomenon caused ageing deterioration on surface of HDPE cable spacer.

After 30,000 tests cycles, damaged surface of tested cable spacers was observed. Tracking and erosion occurred on tested specimen surface. Severe surface erosion was observed on the ground end portion, near ground end and trunk between sheds near ground end, as illustrated in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4 Discharge Activities

Fig. 5 Tracking and Erosion After Tested [Specimen 4]

B. Contamination Degree

Contamination degree was determined by measuring salt deposit density (SDD). The measurement procedures were based on IEC 60507 [13]. After 30,000 tests cycles, SDD measurement results on the whole surface of each specimen as shown in Table II. No difference contamination degree was measured.

TABLE II
 SDD AFTER 30,000 TEST CYCLES

SDD, mg/cm ²			
Specimen 1	Specimen 2	Specimen 3	Specimen 4
0.0130	0.0139	0.0143	0.0130

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C.ATR-FTIR Analysis Result

In order to confirmed surface ageing, chemical analysis by ATR-FTIR (attenuated total reflection fourier transform infrared spectroscopy) was conducted to evaluate any chemical change on tested specimen. For HDPE, C-H bonds at wave number 2916, 2847 and 1462 cm^{-1} indicate side chain and C-C bonds at wave number 720 cm^{-1} indicates back bone of polyethylene molecule [14]-[15]. Position on tested specimen surface for chemical analysis is shown in Fig. 6.

Appearance of C=O bond at wave number $1,745\text{cm}^{-1}$ and C=C bond at wave number $1,630\text{cm}^{-1}$ indicates the occurrence of Oxidation and Carbonization, respectively. As illustrated in Fig. 7, reduction in C-H bond and C-C bond were observed on all tested specimens when comparing with new specimen. In contrast, increasing in C=O bond and C=C bond were observed on all tested specimens. Ratio of C=O bond and C-C bond is illustrated in Fig. 8. And ratio of C=C bond and C-C bond is illustrated in Fig. 9

Fig. 6 Position for ATR-FTIR analysis

Fig. 7 ATR-FTIR analysis result [Position 1]

Fig. 8 Ratio of C=O/C-C

Fig. 9 Ratio of C=C/CC

IV. CONCLUSION

Ageing deterioration of high-density polyethylene cable spacer under salt water dip wheel test based on IEC 62217 have been studied. After 30,000 test cycles, surface tracking and ground end erosion were observed on the specimen surface. Dry band arc discharge and corona discharge caused surface damaging of the tested specimen surface. Salt deposit density of tested specimen surface less than 0.02 mg/cm² was measured. ATR-FTIR analysis results confirm the difference in degree of surface deterioration of HDPE cable spacer under the salt water dip wheel test.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. C. C. Rocha, R.C. Berrêdo, R. A. O. Bernis, E. M. Gomes and F. Nishimura, "New technologies, standards, and maintenance methods in spacer cable systems," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 17, pp. 562-568, April 2002.
- [2] J. D. Bouford, "Spacer cable reduces tree caused customer interruptions," IEEE, 2008,
- [3] Metropolitan Electricity Authority, "Ceramic cable spacer improvement for power quality problem mitigation," *Power Quality Case Study*, Thailand, 2008.
- [4] W. Pinheiro, A. G. Kanashiro and G. F. Burani, "Evaluation of distribution line spacers located near the coast," *WSEAS Transactions on Systems*, vol. 7, pp. 1371-1380, December 2008.
- [5] I. Ramirez-Vazquez, and F.P. Espino-Cortes, "Electric-Field Analysis of Spacer Cable Systems for Compact Overhead Distribution Lines", *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, Vol. 27, No. 4, pp. 2312 – 2317, October 2012.
- [6] F.P. Espino-Cortes, and I.R. Vazquez, "Three dimensional electric field analysis in spacer cable systems", *2012 Annual Report Conference on Electrical Insulation and Dielectric Phenomena (CEIDP)*, pp. 174 – 177, October 2012.
- [7] V. Saithongin, and B. Techaumnat, "Numerical analysis of electric field at the contact point between a spacer aerial cable and a spacer", *International Conference on Electrical Engineering and Informatics (ICEEI)*, pp. 1-5, July 2011.
- [8] M.R. Soares, F.R. Britto, F. Nishimura, and L.D. Cicarelli, "Spacer cable and ABC distribution lines. Long-term analysis", *Proceedings of IEEE Transmission and Distribution Conference*, pp. 219-224, September 1996.
- [9] R.T. Harrold, and T.W. Dakin, "On predicting the life of polyethylene spacer-cable eroded by surface discharges in wet weather",

IEEE Transactions on Power Apparatus and Systems, Vol. 95, No. 3 Part 1, pp. 821-828, May 1976.

- [10] J.D. Bouford, "Spacer cable reduces tree caused customer interruptions", *IEEE/PES Transmission and Distribution Conference and Exposition*, pp. 1-3, April 2008.
- [11] IEC 62217, Committed Draft, September, Ed. 1.0, 2002.
- [12] J. Grasaesom, S.Thong-Om, W. Payakcho and B. Marungsri, "Ageing deterioration of silicone rubber polymer insulator under salt water dip wheel test," *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology*, pp. 211-217, 2011.
- [13] IEC 60507, Artificial pollution tests on high-voltage insulators to be used on AC systems, Ed. 2 b, 1991.
- [14] A.E. Davies and D.A. Hodgson, "Electrical ageing effects in polyethylene," University of Southampton, U.K., pp. 254-257.
- [15] J. A. Mergos, M. D.Athanassopoulou, T. G. Argyropoulos and C. T. Dervos, "The effect of accelerated UV-Ageing on the dielectric properties of PVC, PTFE and HDPE," *International Conference on Solid Dielectrics*, Germany, 2010.

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